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AESTHETIC APPRECIATION AS A MATTER OF EXPERTISE IN CAR DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

The paper reports a study on expertise-determined perception and evaluation differences between designers and design-inexperienced recipients when judging car-exterior models varying systematically in innovativeness and balance. Following the assumptions of Leder, Belke, Oeberst, and Augustin (2004), gaze behaviour, attractiveness assessments, and affective state of 11 designers, 11 engineers, and 11 humanities scholars were collected in a three-phased repeated measurement quasi-experiment. Group comparisons confirmed the proposed interaction of stimulus properties and expertise, while unexpected findings regarding aesthetic emotions were observed.

Keywords: design expertise, innovativeness, aesthetic user requirements

INTRODUCTION

Car designers are experts on creating car exteriors that communicate a brand's identity by giving form to its values which is to appeal to a multitude of customers (Giannini & Monti, 2003; Karjalainen, 2002). In this creative interpretational process it is important to apprehend the customers' requirements as the designer's understanding of these needs and thus of the design problem itself has a major impact on the quality of the design (Ulrich, 2006). One basis for this apprehension is shared contextual knowledge stemming from a successful interaction between the designer and the user (Lee, Popovich, Blackler, & Lee, 2009). However, there often is no direct exchange between designers and users (Zeisel, 2006).

What is more, findings from research on the fine arts and product aesthetics suggest that acquiring aesthetic knowledge and expertise distinctly alter a person's cognitive processing of aesthetic objects, which also manifests in perception, assessment, and behaviour. Together with an increasing autonomy from common opinions and shared taste due to developing aesthetic expertise (cp., Parsons, 1986, 1987), designers' aesthetic preferential assessments are to be expected to differ from the ones of users. Considering these propositions, the current study was conducted to systematically examine these expertise-induced differences between design experts and laymen in perceiving and assessing automotive design. The study is part of a PhD-project (cf. Oehme, submitted for assessment). Theoretical assumptions were based on the model of aesthetic appreciation by Leder, Belke, Oeberst, and Augustin (2004), which provides detailed but hitherto untested assumptions on how experts and laymen differ in their processing of aesthetic objects. Testing these assumptions, we hope to contribute to furthering the interaction between designers and users by establishing a shared knowledge base and by quantifying expertise-dependent differences in aesthetic perception and preferences.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

DESIGN EXPERTS AND KNOWLEDGE

Experts in general have acquired more knowledge in a certain domain than other people (cp. Chase & Simon, 1973a, 1973b; cf. Ericsson & Smith, 1991, Ericsson, 2008, for an overview). Their knowledge is well organized and structured, and strongly cross-linked (see Bedard & Chi, 1992; Chi, 2006 for an overview). Nevertheless, following a relative

approach of design research, the fundamental capacities and general cogitation of experts and laymen are thought to be more or less identical: Performance differences between the two are determined by differences in knowledge representation (cp. Chi, 2006). But what qualities especially define design expertise? Wölfel and Prescher (2008, p.288) provide a comprehensive definition of design knowledge: Design knowledge, as expert knowledge in other domains, is based on experience (see Ericsson, 2006 for an overview). It comprises episodic and declarative knowledge as well as socio-cultural and common knowledge. Design knowledge is tacit and objective in that it is directed towards formal design aspects, however it is also subjective in that it is based on integrated experience. Finally, design knowledge is emotionally directed towards the user experiencing the design object. Design knowledge thus is a cognitive competency which is more or less distinct (cp. Chi, 2006). However, compared to many other expert domains which have been investigated so far, design knowledge is per se strongly related to the effects of the respective design solution on subject-unfamiliar persons, i.e. users.

MANIFESTATIONS OF DESIGN EXPERTISE

Establishing *expertise* in an aesthetic domain such as the fine arts, architecture or product design is associated with a number of changes in perception, problem solving, and aesthetic judgment. Art experts perceive rather style-oriented and thereby explore visual scenes with regard to style while art-inexperienced persons explore paintings less focussedly (Nodine, Locher, & Krupinski, 1993; Waligorska, 2006). They exert more specific¹ gaze behaviour in free exploration sessions (Vogt & Magnussen, 2007). Similarly, Rähä et al. (2006) found higher proportions of specific gaze behaviour when designers, compared to users, evaluated mobile phones during thinking aloud sessions.

¹ Berlyne (1971) differentiated between diversive and specific explorative behavior, the former being driven by a search for stimulation and entertainment, the latter being driven by curiosity due to increased interpretational demands. Specific exploration manifests in fixation clusters while diversive exploration is characterised by a lack of fixation clusters during viewing.

In solving design problems, designers use *knowledge inversion*, i.e. an iterative application of concept-based or declarative knowledge on a given design problem (cp. Feltovich, Prietula, & Ericsson, 2006) and integrate various stakeholder requirements (Cross, 2003), while design students proceed serially and not problem-focussedly (Christiaans, 1992). Design experts exert a more progressive visual reasoning than novices with a higher productivity and modification frequency in sketching design ideas (Kavakli, Suwa, Gero & Purcell, 1999). Expert design activity seems more structured, organized, and efficient than that of novices (Kavakli & Gero, 2002) and the representation of their knowledge seems to correspond with Chase's and Simon's (1973b) early findings of expert chess players' large quantities of knowledge represented in chunks.

In judging aesthetic objects of their domain, art experts classify (Augustin & Leder, 2006; Waligorska, 2006) and interpret (Schmidt, McLaughlin, & Leighton, 1989) regarding to style rather than self-oriented. Art-educated recipients rather prefer abstract art while art-inexperienced recipients assign higher preferential ratings to representational art (Lengger, Fischmeister, Leder, & Bauer, 2007; Uusitalo, Simola, & Kuisma, 2009). Architects prefer different material (Köhler, 2009) and assess architectural design differently in terms of structural, economic, and aesthetic aspects than citizens (Benz & Rambow, 2008). What is more, Nasar (1989) not only found differences in aesthetic assessments between laymen and architects but the experts also misjudged the preferences of the participating citizens for the investigated house styles.

WHY CAR DESIGN?

Nowadays, building a brand and an image in the automotive industries is substantially linked to design in terms of the design vocabulary of car models or product ranges (Landmann & Reichle, 2004; Schmidt, 2003), because high technological standards of virtually all manufacturers (apart from fuel efficiency) present only limited possibilities to differentiate in function (Braess & Seiffert, 2005; Sjudell, 2003). Brand loyalty is decreasing continually in such a way, that the actual selection of a brand in a purchase decision and the initial

brand preference may diverge substantially (Köcher & Hallemann, 2004; cp. Lorenz, 1986). This development constitutes one reason for aggravated competitive conditions on saturated markets, which leads to intensified canvassing (Blöcker & Jürgens, 2008). At this, *design innovation* represents an essential success factor for vehicle sales (Talke, Salomo, Wieringa, & Lutz, 2009; cp. Cox, 2005). New marketing studies show empirical evidence that good industrial design, in terms of its form, correlates with a positive financial performance (Hertenstein, Platt, & Veryzer, 2005). Talke et al. (2009) conducted a comprehensive study with 157 new car models introduced between 1978 and 2006 on the German market and showed that design innovativeness resembles a crucial factor for vehicle sales with a strong effect on number of sales in the first year of sale and a remaining significant effect in the subsequent years. Innovative design thus builds a bridge between aesthetic and economic aspects of the product *car* (cp. Hatchuel, Starkey, Tempest, & Le Masson, 2010).

The extent of innovativeness and novelty, however, determines whether a presented form is accepted or rejected (Rindova & Petkova, 2007). Rindova and Petkova (2007) provide a framework for the *perceived value* of products based on the schema approach of Mandler (1982) whereas attributes (or products) are preferred, which correspond with a person's activated or available schema. Slight incongruity is experienced as interesting and evaluated positively (cp. also Berlyne, 1971), while substantial incongruity with an available schema leads to a negative (product) assessment (Mandler, 1982; Rindova & Petkova, 2007). According to Rindova & Petkova (2007) this evaluative process also influences the perceived value of a product accordingly.

Carbon and Leder (2005) define innovativeness as „originality by virtue of introducing new ideas“ (p.587). Thus, innovative product design contains forms whose genuine feature *innovativeness* already suggests that it is at least slightly more incongruent with existing customer schemata than that of products with common styling (cp. Henderson & Clark, 1990). Hence, designing cars seems to be a balancing act between creating unique design with large market success and forming a product which is

too uncommon for the target customers and consequently does not sell satisfactorily (Sjodell, 2003).

In a study with an a priori classification of design experts and non-experts based on field of studies, Hung and Chen (2009) showed strong effects of expertise for aesthetic preferences regarding 88 versions of seating furniture: Design students, compared to engineering and marketing students, preferred novel, less prototypical design. The researchers therewith substantiated earlier and less pronounced finding of Leder and Carbon (2005) who applied a median split of art interest to compare groups of different aesthetic expertise while investigating preference ratings for interior car design.

Together with findings from expertise research showing that aesthetics experts have difficulties in estimating preferences of non-experts (Bromme, 2000; Bromme & Rambow, 1995; Nasar, 1989) and in engaging with users and structuring the collected information (Lai & Yang, 2009), a thorough investigation of the effect of car design innovativeness on designers and customers might add valuable information to the design process.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Given the empirical evidence, there are surprisingly few theoretical frameworks which explicitly deal with expertise as a crucial factor for art and product appreciation. User or recipient characteristics such as experience, personality, or motives are considered for example by Desmet and Hekkert (2007), who provide a framework for *aesthetic product experience* as well as by Locher, Overbeeke and Wensveen (2010) within their framework of *aesthetic interaction*. However, no specific assumptions regarding the impact of the respective level of experience on aesthetic judgments are discussed.

Leder et al. (2004) provide such a framework with their model of *aesthetic appreciation and aesthetic judgments*. Therein, an aesthetic experience is described as a cognitive process which proceeds from mainly bottom-up based perception to higher levels of interpretational processing of aesthetic objects, resulting in an aesthetic judgment and an aesthetic emotion, the latter of which is based on the

perceived success in processing the aesthetic object (cp. Belke & Leder, 2006). The aesthetic emotion thus represents the results of an appraisal process (Lazarus 2001; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Leder et al. (2004) assume that their postulated cognitive and affective experiences are interdependent and proceed in iterative and incrementing loops (cp. also Silvia, 2005b). Expertise moderates the information processing because art experts can draw from domain specific and declarative knowledge and thus master an aesthetic object, especially in the higher processing levels, with higher quality than art-inexperienced persons. In the higher level processing stage *explicit classification* an object is classified regarding to style and content. Leder and colleagues (2004), in accordance with Parsons' (1987) development stages for art expertise, postulate that art experts use visual style features for processing and classification while art-inexperienced recipients assess more self-related and orientate on content and external standards.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND HYPOTHESES

The goal of the study was to verify key assumptions of the model of Leder et al. (2004) in the domain of car design by investigating the expertise-determined evaluation of car-exterior models. In addition to Leder and colleagues' (2004) postulations of processing-related differences between experts and laymen, hypotheses regarding the effect of stimulus properties important for automotive design and their interaction with design expertise were addressed. Besides *innovativeness* the impact of a variation of *balance* was investigated. Balance refers to harmonic proportions or a harmonic weighting of elements in a composition which then form an impression of unity (Wilson & Chatterjee, 2005). Balance is widely preferred (e.g., Locher, 2003; Locher & Nodine, 1987; Locher & Nodine, 1989; Tinio & Leder, 2009; Veryzer, 1993) because it seems to support processing (e.g., Enquist & Arak, 1994; Enquist & Johnstone, 1997). While both, art laymen and experts, successfully discriminate between harmonically and non-harmonically organized pictorial stimuli, only the latter seem to be sensitive to subtle variations in balance (Locher, 2003; Locher, Stappers, & Overbeeke, 1999). A change in compositional balance may lead to differences in

visual exploration behavior between experts and laymen, because experts recognize the violation of design principle (Nodine et al., 1993). To summarise: Attractiveness

H1a: Designers and laymen do not differ in their appreciation of balanced design - balanced design is preferred (cp. Locher, 2003).

H1b: Designers rate highly innovative design as most attractive while design-inexperienced persons prefer designs of low and moderate innovativeness (cp. Hung & Chen, 2009).

Emotional state and perceived successfulness

Designers and laymen differ in their perceived success in mastering the design evaluation and in their affective state:

H2a: Due to their expertise, designers are more successful in mastering the judgment task than laymen and

H2b: perceive higher levels of activation and a more positive emotional state.

Gaze behaviour

H3: Designers and laymen differ in gaze behaviour: compared to laymen, designers exert more diverse visual exploration when perceiving unusual, i.e. highly novel and imbalanced design (cp. Nodine et al., 1993).

METHOD

PARTICIPANTS

The study was conducted as quasi-experiment with 11 product designers aged 28 to 35 years ($M=31.2$; 2 females; 2 students) with experience in car design via project work or a professional career at a car manufacturer. Two profession-wise homogenous groups of 11 engineers aged 20 to 44 years ($M=31.6$; 3 females; 5 students) and 11 humanities scholars aged 29 to 45 years ($M=34.6$; 6 females; 3 students) all without experience in car design constituted the design-inexperienced test groups. All participants were emmetrope or used visual aids to ensure emmetropia during the experimental session. They received a financial compensation for their participation.

MEASUREMENT AND MATERIAL

The hypotheses were tested via repeated measurement design with three test phases:

- I. design evaluation with eye-tracking
- II. repeated evaluation technique (Carbon & Leder, 2005) without eye-tracking
- III. design evaluation with eye-tracking

Stimulus presentation and gaze capture were realized via the binocular eye-tracker system Tobii T120, which operates with a 17"-monitor with a resolution of 1280x1024 pixels. The Tobii-compatible open-source software Ogama (OpenGazeAndMouseAnalyser) was applied, which allows for a simultaneous capture and analysis of eye and mouse data during the processing of presentation slides (Voßkuehler, 2010). The repeated evaluation phase was carried out on a second computer working station with the same monitor size and settings but without an eye-tracker. Following Leder and Carbon (2005), nine pretested line drawings of exterior design models varying systematically in innovativeness and balance were presented, which had been prepared by a product designer. Innovativeness was varied via the B-pillar construction and its continuation at the door crack, the lateral bumpers and the lateral line and front design. Balance variation was realized via tire diameter and greenhouse height.

Figure 1. Stimuli: line drawings of car models varying in innovativeness and balance in three levels. Innovativeness progresses i1 (prototypical), i2 (moderate), i3 (highly innovative). Balance progresses b1 (balanced), b2 (moderate), b3 (imbalanced).

The affective state was evaluated via SAM-ratings (Lang, 1980) prior to and after test phase I and III. All other ratings were assessed on 6-point-Likert-scales with the poles 1 corresponding to “not at all” and 6 corresponding to “very much”. Perceived

assurance and satisfaction were rated twice during the session.

Following the experimental approach of Carbon and colleagues (Carbon, 2010b; Carbon, Hutzler, & Minge, 2006; Carbon & Leder, 2005; Faerber, Leder, Gerger, & Carbon, 2010; Gerger, Leder, Faerber & Carbon, in press), aesthetic appreciation was operationalised by the questions on how attractive, innovative, and well-proportioned (in terms of balance) the presented car model was perceived. The repeated evaluation was assessed via 22 pretested items capturing the dimensions attractiveness, dynamics, progress, and quality (cf. Oehme, submitted for assessment)².

PROCEDURE

The participants proceeded individually through the three test phases. After receiving an oral introduction, the participant took a seat in front of the eye-tracker working station, was calibrated, and subsequently received an instruction presentation with a training trial. The first phase of the test session started with an assessment of the emotional state, which was followed by the car model assessment in the order attractiveness, innovativeness, and balance (cp. Carbon & Leder, 2005). The order of the line drawings was randomized for each subject. Each line drawing was presented for seven seconds. This test phase was finished after a second emotional assessment and assessment of perceived assurance and satisfaction. For the second phase, the participant changed to the working station without eye-tracker and proceeded through the 22 items per car model in order to prevent fatigue due to restricted seating conditions in front of the eye-tracker. Line drawings and items were presented in randomized order. For the third phase, the participant returned to the eye-tracker working station and followed the procedure of phase one, again starting with the calibration and the assessment of his emotional state. The complete test procedure took about one hour.

² In German: Attraktivität, Dynamik, Fortschritt und Qualität.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We will first focus on the rating results to analyse the expected group differences for attractiveness assessments and to check whether the manipulation of the factors *innovativeness* and *balance* was perceived accordingly by the participants. Subsequently, the ratings regarding emotional state, perceived assurance, and satisfaction are analysed and finally the analysis of the gaze data is reported. Results of the repeated evaluation phase are reported elsewhere (cf. Oehme, submitted for assessment).

ATTRACTIVENESS RATINGS

The variation of the stimulus material regarding innovativeness and balance affected the ratings of design experts and inexperienced participants as

Figure 2. Average attractiveness ratings for designers, engineers, and humanities scholars.

expected (cp. Figure 2): Overall, the attractiveness ratings decreased with balance level for all groups with the highly balanced models b1 receiving the highest attractiveness ratings ($b1 > b2 > b3$). Designers rated the car models low and medium in innovativeness (i1 and i2) as less attractive and the highly innovative models as more attractive (i3) than the inexperienced participants, while the rating pattern of the inexperienced recipients favoured the car models medium and low in innovativeness. Mean attractiveness ratings for each group were submitted to a mixed repeated measurement ANOVA with the between-subjects factor *group* and the within-subjects factors *innovativeness*, *balance*, and *test*

phase. The factor *innovativeness* showed a large effect of $f=0.55$ with $F(1.58, 47.29)=8.97$, $p<0.01$, $(1 - \beta)=0.93$ as well as the factors *balance* with $f=1.67$ and $F(1.38, 1.33)=83.58$, $p<0.01$, $(1 - \beta)=1.00$, and *test phase* with $f=0.90$ and $F(1, 30)=24.06$, $p<0.01$, $(1 - \beta)=1.00$. The *group*-factor was not significant with $F(2, 30)=0.98$, $p=0.39$, $(1 - \beta)=0.21$ and a moderate effect of $f=0.25$.

The interaction between *balance* and *group* showed no significant effect, as expected in H1a, with $F(2.76, 41.33)=0.53$, $p=0.65$, $f=0.19$, $(1 - \beta)=0.15$. As expected in H1b, the interaction between *innovativeness* and *group* showed a large effect of $f=0.58$ with $F(3.15, 47.29)=4.97$, $p<0.01$, $(1 - \beta)=0.90$. Bonferroni-adjusted tests revealed significant group differences between designers and engineers with $T(20)=-3.54$, $p<0.005$, $d=1.51$ as well as between designers and humanities scholars with $T(20)=-4.02$, $p<0.005$, $d=1.82$ for innovativeness level i1. Significant interaction effects of *innovativeness* and *balance* $F(4, 120)=15.29$, $p<0.01$, $f=0.71$, $(1 - \beta)=1.00$ as well as *innovativeness*, *balance* and *group* with $F(8, 120)=2.49$, $p<0.05$, $f=0.41$, $(1 - \beta)=0.89$ substantiated the expected evaluation pattern (Figure 2). Additionally, a substantial interaction between *test phase* and *balance* was observed with $F(2, 60)=12.09$, $p<0.01$, $f=0.63$, $(1 - \beta)=0.99$ with increasing attractiveness ratings after the repeated evaluation phase for balance levels b1 with $T(32)=-6.08$, $p<0.01$, $d_z=-1.06$ and b2 with $T(32)=-3.69$, $p<0.01$, $d_z=0.64$. This trend was also found for the interaction between *innovativeness* and *test phase*, which however did not reach statistical significance with $F(1.67, 50.20)=2.36$, $p=0.11$, $f=0.28$, $(1 - \beta)=0.42$. No other effects were statistically significant.

MANIPULATION OF INNOVATIVENESS & BALANCE

The manipulation check was conducted for innovativeness and balance ratings in a mixed repeated measurement ANOVA with the between-subjects factor *group* and the within-subjects factors *innovativeness* and *test phase* or *balance* and *test phase*, respectively. For innovativeness ratings, the factor *innovativeness* showed a strong main effect with $f=1.66$ and $F(1.53; 45.82)=82.60$, $p<0.01$, $(1 - \beta)=1.00$ as well as the factor *test phase* with

$F(1; 30)=11.30, p<0.01, f=0.61, (1 - \beta)=0.90$. The average innovativeness ratings increased after repeated evaluation from $M=2.97 (SE=0.14)$ to $M=3.30 (SE=0.08)$. The interaction between *innovativeness* and *test phase* showed a large effect of $F(2; 60)=5.16, p<0.01, f=0.42, (1 - \beta)=0.81$. The factor *group* was significant as well with $F(2; 30)=4.72, p<0.05, f=0.56, (1 - \beta)=0.75$ in that designers on average assigned significantly lower innovativeness ratings [$M=2.68 (SE=0.18)$] than engineers [$M=3.38 (SE=0.18)$] and humanities scholars [$M=3.22 (SE=0.18)$] with Scheffé: $p<0.05$. For balance ratings, solely the factor *balance* showed a strong main effect of $f=2.19$ with $F(1.58, 47.41)=144.01, p<0.01, (1 - \beta)=1.00$.

PERCEIVED ASSURANCE & SATISFACTION

Perceived assurance and satisfaction were assessed twice during a test session. At the first measurement, designers felt surer than the engineers and the humanities scholars (cp. Table 1). No effect was of statistical significance³.

	designers		engineers		humanities	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
I	5.18	0.98	4.55	0.69	4.91	0.94
II	5.00	0.78	4.82	0.75	5.09	0.83

Table 1. Perceived assurance during task completion

At both measurements of perceived satisfaction with their own task performance, humanities scholars scored highest (cp. Table 2).

	designers		engineers		humanities	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
I	4.73	1.02	4.73	0.79	5.36	0.51
II	4.55	0.82	5.00	0.89	5.36	0.51

Table 2. Perceived satisfaction with own task performance

The group differences were contrary to expectations of H2a and the factor *group* showed a strong but non-significant effect with $F(1, 30)=3.23, p=0.05, f=0.46, (1 - \beta)=0.57$. No other effects were of statistical significance⁴.

³ [measurement: $F(1, 30)=0.53, p=0.47, f=0.13, (1 - \beta)=0.11$; group: $F(1, 30)=0.89, p=0.42, f=0.24, (1 - \beta)=0.19$ interaction: $F(2, 30)=1.24, p=0.31, f=0.29, (1 - \beta)=0.25$]

⁴ [measurement: $F(1, 30)=0.06, p=0.81, f=0.04, (1 - \beta)=0.06$; interaction: $F(2, 30)=1.09, p=0.35, f=0.27, (1 - \beta)=0.22$]

EMOTIONAL STATE

The SAM-scales for arousal and valence (Lang, 1980) were applied to measure the subjective emotional state of participants. The first measurement of the emotional state was tested separately in order to determine the overall initial state of the participants. Here, no group differences were desired. Preferably, the initial affective state was to

Figure 3. Average arousal ratings with standard error of designers, engineers, and humanities scholars for the four measurements during the experimental session.

be activated and of positive to neutral valence. Figure 3 and Figure 4 provide an overview of all four measurements during a test session.

As preferred, the initial affective state was of rather neutral arousal and positive valence. There was no significant group difference for both scales with $F(2, 30)=1.79, p=0.19, f=0.34, (1 - \beta)=0.38$ for arousal and $F(2, 30)=1.41, p=0.26, f=0.31, (1 - \beta)=0.30$ for valence.

Figure 4. Average valence ratings with standard error of designers, engineers, and humanities scholars for the four measurements during the experimental session.

As to be expected, arousal decreased during the test session (cp. Figure 3). Contrary to our hypothesis H2b, designers felt less activated than the design inexperienced groups at all points of measurement during the experiment.

The within-subjects factor *measurement* showed a strong effect with $F(2, 60)=4.57$, $p<0.05$, $f=0.39$, $(1 - \beta)=0.76$ whereas the factor *group* with $F(1, 30)=0.48$, $p=0.62$, $f=0.18$, $(1 - \beta)=0.12$ as well as their interaction with $F(2, 60)=0.33$, $p=0.86$, $f=0.15$, $(1 - \beta)=0.12$ were of no statistical significance. The humanities scholars had the most positive state during the test. The factor *measurement* showed only a trend with $F(2, 60)=2.84$, $p=0.07$, $f=0.31$, $(1 - \beta)=0.54$ which, however, was not in line with our hypothesis. The factor *group* with $F(1, 30)=0.29$, $p=0.75$, $f=0.14$, $(1 - \beta)=0.09$ and the interaction of *measurement* and *group* with $F(2, 60)=1.17$, $p=0.33$, $f=0.28$, $(1 - \beta)=0.35$ were again not significant.

GAZE BEHAVIOUR

Following the test settings of Nodine et al. (1993), the proportion of short to long gazes as manifestation of diversive gaze behavior was explored in the first test phase during attractiveness ratings after the first two seconds of viewing time, i.e. when a first orientation phase has been completed (cp. also Locher, 2006; Molnar, 1981)⁵. The descriptive data is provided in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Average gaze ratio for designers, engineers and humanities scholars; error bars were excluded in favour of legibility.

⁵ Gaze specifications were adopted from Nodine, Kundel, Toto, and Krupinski (1992) with gaze clusters of 2.5° radius, a minimum fixation count of two per cluster and a minimum of fixating time of 38ms.

Imbalanced design was mainly realized by the level of balance (b2 and b3), whereas the impression of unusualness was realized by the higher levels of innovativeness (i2 and i3). The ratio of short to long gazes was only highest for designers for two car models (b2i1, b2i2). None of the main and interaction effects was of statistical significance⁶.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The reported study tested several assumptions of the model of aesthetic appreciation and aesthetic experience by Leder et al. (2004) in a complex laboratory setting. In accordance with Carbon and Leder (2005, Hung & Chen, 2009; cp. also Leder & Carbon, 2005) the results of the study showed that innovative and thus less prototypical automotive design is evaluated as less attractive by design laymen while they assess prototypical design and design of moderate innovativeness as most attractive. Designers show the opposite evaluation pattern and allocate higher attractiveness ratings to highly innovative design. These findings support the assumption that designers, due to their aesthetic experience, can draw from a broader product schema than inexperienced perceivers (cp. Rindova & Petkova, 2007). This conclusion is substantiated by the assessment trend for the innovativeness evaluation: Designers allocated lower innovativeness values to all line models, including highly innovative ones. Working on design problems, they are continuously confronted with new design ideas and are used to master these. Appreciation of new styles may be an expression of Leder et al.'s (2004) postulated characteristic of aesthetic experts. The challenge for experts is to keep in mind the customers' preference of a certain level of typicality which those seem to relate more to than design experts. If car models are extremely innovative, market introduction is supported via contextual information, design studies on relevant trade shows or the introduction of a new product schema, e.g. SUV sport utility vehicle (Rosa, Porac, Runser-Spanjol

⁶ [balance: $F(2, 58)=1.45$, $p=0.24$, $f=0.22$, $(1 - \beta)=0.30$; innovativeness: $F(2, 58)=1.08$, $p=0.35$, $f=0.19$, $(1 - \beta)=0.23$; group: $F(2, 29)=0.23$, $p=0.80$, $f=0.12$, $(1 - \beta)=0.08$; group*balance: $F(4, 120)=0.64$, $p=0.64$, $f=0.21$, $(1 - \beta)=0.20$; group*innovativeness: $F(4, 120)=2.11$, $p=0.09$, $f=0.38$, $(1 - \beta)=0.59$]

& Saxon, 1999). These means help customers to build a relation to the new style and to master the aesthetic experience (Leder et al., 2004) or alternatively enhance their schema of the product 'car' (Rindova & Petkova, 2007).

Surprisingly, the ratings of all groups converged after repeated evaluation. In accordance with findings of Carbon and Leder (2005) as well as Carbon et al. (2006), Carbon et al. (2008) and Gerger et al. (in press) attractiveness ratings increased only for car models of moderate and high innovativeness after repeated evaluation. Prototypical car models received more or less identical attractiveness ratings in phase III. This result challenges Zajonc's (1968) mere exposure effect while providing evidence for an added value of repeated product assessment. Since repeated exploration changes product evaluation, product assessments carried out to substantiate design decisions should incorporate more than one assessment phase in order to validly predict customers' aesthetic choices. This is supported by market research findings regarding purchase decisions (Köcher & Halleemann, 2004; Lorenz, 1986) and in empirical research regarding preference ratings for dresses which change substantially during repeated measurement (Cox & Cox, 2002). It seems that the appreciation of more complex or more innovative products gains from repeated exposure. In terms of Berlyne (1971), their activation level shifts from high to medium and thus their attractiveness increases. Coughlan and Mashman (1999) found preference shifts for vehicle prototypes already after one repetition. These findings are important in view of the fact that purchase decisions are more often preceded by a thorough internet research, i.e. customers become informed (Capgemini, 2010; Köcher & Halleemann, 2004).

What is more, converging ratings for all groups suggest that designers might come to similar aesthetic 'conclusions' as customers after a thorough assessment phase, which could be easily integrated into the design process. However, further research is needed to prove the stability of this effect.

Designers felt less assured and were less satisfied with their task performance. This might be due to the assessment via questionnaire which might have been artificial to designers but more familiar to the humanities scholars, who provided the highest

valence ratings during the whole test session.

Dealing with a task of their field of expertise, designers might also have been more self-critical than the inexperienced participants.

Furthermore, designers were less activated than the inexperienced participant groups, which might again be due to the kind of task to be fulfilled. What is more, the presented car models, being more 'common' for designers than for inexperienced recipients, might have not led to a substantial arousal level for this group.

All groups showed different gaze behaviour which descriptively did not correspond to their attractiveness rating patterns. Presumably, the simple line drawing material did not provide enough visual interpretational complexity for revealing a rather marginal effect of expertise in design perception. This also reflects the trade-off between a clear manipulation of design properties and the rich impression of natural car design. What is more, subtle effects in attention differences between groups of perceivers might not be reflected in a gaze ratio.

The following conclusions can be drawn:

- The model of Leder et al. (2004) can be substantiated with concrete assumptions regarding the interaction of object properties and expert level of the recipient.
- Designers evaluate innovative design as more attractive than design-inexperienced recipients which has an impact on design decisions. This outcome, when considered in the design process, should also benefit design education and user-designer interaction.
- Designers show an independent, autonomous rating behaviour which reflects their higher level of expertise (Parsons, 1987). They can draw from a broad schema when assessing design and are less activated by prototypical design than non-experts.
- Repeated evaluation changes product evaluation which is to be considered when predicting customers' aesthetic choices.

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